

MODERN METHODS IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Rasuljonova Saida

School teacher No. 191 of Tashkent City

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928495>

Abstract: This article perfectly teaches foreign languages in our country and modern methods necessary for learning, as well as a wide range of them the importance of use is illuminated.

Keywords: foreign language, innovative technology, technological tools, modern methods, games

Introduction

In the developing era of today, in each area in particular, in the field of science changes and significant progress are being made. Our country after independence, the focus on science in particular on foreign languages is further intensified. From modern innovative technologies and techniques of each discipline using teaching is one of the most important requirements of today's era. Also, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov after making a number of decisions regarding the teaching and learning of foreign languages a new atmosphere and Era began in our country.

Modern according to the resolution textbooks, methods and technologies were produced. In current modern education interactive methods, innovative technologies, training from information technology the demand for the disposal of the process is growing to day by day. The basic of this is one of the reasons, in contrast to the traditional education that has been up to this time development of the personality of the reader when using modern methods , conditions necessary for the formation, acquisition and upbringing of sufficient knowledge is creating. The role and role of modern methods and innovative technologies so much big is older. There are several ways to teach foreign languages , in particular, English there are effective methods. In particular, video rollers in English in the course of the lesson, showing dialogues, movies or cartoons, was considered a much more traditional way tape recorders and CDs can be used. This is the use of technical means to make the learning process of a foreign language more interesting and effective for students provides. The importance of modern methods in teaching a foreign language is incomparable. Shu using several techniques widely used in the current era are coming. For example:

1. Method 'B-B-B " (we know, we want to know, we know). This method is in the course of the lesson for the growth of students ' ability to understand the text, to interpret it is the desired method.

2."Brainstorming" (brainstorming) is a method of generating ideas is. The essence of this method is based on Team cooperation in students to several stages of solving the problem in time: ideas generation consists in developing them in a critical and constructive state.

3."Problem situation solution" (Creative Problem Solving). Using this method for the beginning part of the story is read and its ending part is finding is a reference to readers ' judgment. This method is thinking in the reader promotes the development of abilities.

4.'Quick answers " is a topic that is addressed to readers in this a question is asked on the surface. This method serves to increase the effectiveness of the mentioned lesson.

5."Pantomime" (Pantomime) is a variety of words through gestures explanation.This method is used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or aim when students who perform written exercises are used in times of exhaustion is appropriate.

6."Story chain" (a chain story) a story is told. This method develops students oral speech.

7.The'when pictures speak " method is much more convenient, with English helps in teaching the language, in the development of students oral speech, to do this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic.

8."Quiz cards" - depending on the number of readers in this Cards are distributed and all students participate in the lesson at the same time provides, which saves a lot of time.

9."Cluster" method. Clustering to students on a topic it is a pedagogical strategy that helps to think freely and openly.

This the method is mainly to evoke new thoughts, add new thoughts to existing knowledge again is an effective method for.

10.The "Insert" method. In this, Readers are presented with a text or story and students are required to retell it. This method is with the text to support activity, observability and understanding when working is a strong method. Hence, in teaching foreign languages of each method, as shown above there are effective methods. Modern in each lesson in the process of teaching the effective use of pedagogical technologies and techniques makes students to think independently and freely, to seek, to take each issue seriously, helps to strengthen their interest in acquiring knowledge.

As well as the teacher when a student is able to organize a collaborative activity , both have a positive result can reach. In conclusion, the edge in the

period of today's fierce rebirth in an era when the need to teach their language was high, Modern in the educational process the effective use of methods, innovative educational technologies is the process is allowed to be fast and efficient. In particular, technological tools edge each of the language learning skills(reading, writing, listening and understanding and speak).

Our country's education system is perfect, mature and as the freethinker sets himself the goal of nurturing the individual, we are all future teachers studied modern methods and technologies excellent teaching of foreign languages to young people with effective use of them through which we can contribute to the prosperity of our country.

References:

1. Bekmurodova.U. B. "From innovative technologies in learning English abstract on the topic "use"., Tashkent 2012.
2. Khatamova N. Q., Mirzayeva M. N. "Applied in English classes interactive rules " (methodological manual) , Navoi. 2006,40 PP.
3. Yakubov I."English teaching methodology", (tutorial). Tashkent, Oriental publications. 2003 < BR >
4. Ahrorovna, N. N. ., & Marcona, M.. (2021). Improving Important Memory Techniques in the teaching and training process. & quote; online - Conferences & quot; platform,
- 5.Retrieved from <http://papers.online-conferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/589>
6. Saidova, M. U. (2019). Lexical stylistic tools and literary terms Figurative Language. International Journal of recent technology and engineering (IJRTE), ISSN, 2277-3878.- content/downloads/papers / v8i3S / c10541083s19.pdf.

